

Grant Agreement number: 101181746

Project acronym: 4Sir2

Project title: 4Sir2 Smoothy: Building a Healthy Drink Ecosystem to Prevent Childhood Obesity

Disclaimer:

This deliverable has been submitted to the European Commission and is currently under review. The final version after the approval may differ.

Deliverable 1.2

Guideline for Ethical Research

Delivery type	Other
Lead beneficiary	RIC
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Contribution	ICZMP
Contractual delivery date	30.11.2025
Delivery date	29.11.2025
Dissemination level	Public

Funded by
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HISTORY OF CHANGES			
Version	Date	Author/Contributor	Changes
01	24.10.2025	RIC	First draft
02	02.11.2025	RIC	Internal consultations
03	06.11.2025	ICZMP	Contribution in the aspect of clinical research has been clarified and aligned with the project's objectives.
04	07.11.2025	SC Members	Consultation during SC meeting
05	12.11.2025	RIC	Draft ready for Consortium revision
06	21.11.2025	All partners	Corrections and additions
07	27.11.2025	RIC/ICZMP	Implementation of the changes suggested by the partners.
08	29.11.2025	RIC	Final version

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1. Introduction

Research conducted under Horizon Europe must meet the highest ethical standards. Ethics is not an isolated element, but a transversal requirement that protects the rights, safety, and dignity of all project partners and research participants, ensures the responsible use of data and technologies and promotes the well-being of the environment and society. The 4Sir2 Ethical Research Guidelines provide a common reference point for all 4Sir2 partners, ensuring that projects are conducted in full compliance with EU ethical principles, national regulations, and best scientific practices.

1.1. Purpose of the Document

The purpose of this document is to provide clear, practical ethical guidelines for all partners involved in the 4Sir2 project.

It aims to:

- establish shared standards for ethical conduct across all Work Packages (WPs),
- support partners in identifying, assessing and mitigating ethical risks,
- ensure that conducted activities comply with the ethics requirements set by Horizon Europe Programme and the Grant Agreement,
- guide partners in responsible design, implementation and reporting of activities,
- ensure consistency between the ethical approach of the project and its Data Management Plan (DMP), dissemination strategy, and fieldwork practices.

This document should be used as a reference for planning, implementation and reporting of research tasks within 4Sir2.

1.2. Scope and Relevance for 4Sir2

The scope of these guidelines encompasses all activities carried out within the 4Sir2 project, including:

- technological development (drying systems, optoelectronics, sensory systems, optimization of biocomponent extraction processes, production of fertilization, grape pellets, etc.),
- development of functional beverages and food products,
- medical and genetic research involving children and young adults,
- consumer research, including sensory studies and market analyses,
- agricultural research on vineyards and grape pomace,
- data management, legal framework, AI-based analytics, and digital tools used in the project.

Due to the multidisciplinary nature of the 4Sir2 project, ethical considerations apply across multiple dimensions: human subjects, biospecimens, food safety, law regulations, technological testing, data management, environmental impact, and responsible

communication. This document ensures that all these aspects are addressed consistently and proactively.

1.3. Ethics Requirements in Horizon Europe

Horizon Europe sets strict ethics requirements that must be met throughout the entire lifecycle of the project.

These requirements include:

- compliance with EU legislation, including GDPR (Regulation EU 2016/679), food law regulations (e.g. Regulation EU 2015/2283, Regulation EU 1924/2006), the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, and relevant national laws;
- ensuring voluntary and informed consent for any involvement of human participants;
- protection of personal data and sensitive information;
- lowering of risks to participants, researchers and the environment;
- safeguards for vulnerable groups, such as children and their families;
- ethical use of technologies, digital tools and AI systems;
- compliance with Open Science principles while ensuring confidentiality where required;
- continuous monitoring of ethical issues and reporting to the European Commission.

Compliance with ethical principles must be ensured by the Coordinator, WP Leaders, and all members of the 4Sir2 consortium throughout the project; failure to comply may result in the suspension of specific activities or other corrective actions required by the European Commission.

1.4. Key Ethical Principles Guiding the Project

The 4Sir2 project is guided by generally recognized ethical standards for scientific research, including:

- Respect for human dignity and autonomy: ensuring voluntary participation, informed consent, and the right to withdraw at any time.
- Benchmarking and non-maleficence: maximizing benefits and minimizing risks for research participants, project partners, communities, and the environment.
- Justice and fairness: ensuring equal treatment, avoiding discrimination, and ensuring equitable access to the benefits of research.
- Scientific integrity and honesty: ensuring transparency, accuracy, and reproducibility of research.
- Data responsibility: protecting privacy, securing data flows, and ensuring GDPR compliance.

- Environmental responsibility: minimizing negative environmental impacts and supporting sustainable practices.
- Responsible innovation: ensuring the appropriate, ethical, and safe use of new technologies, including AI-based tools, if developed.

These principles underpin all research decisions and practices within the project.

1.5. Ethical Issues Identified in the Ethics Review

During the ethical review of the 4Sir2 proposal, several key ethical issues were identified that require ongoing attention:

- The involvement of participants, including vulnerable groups with obesity, e.g. children and their families, and young adults, in nutritional, physiological, and genetic research.
- The processing of personal and sensitive data, especially health data, requires strict compliance with the law, including GDPR.
- The collection and analysis of food and physiological samples, which requires appropriate handling, anonymization, and storage procedures.
- The use of digital technologies and artificial intelligence tools, which must be transparent, understandable, and compliant with EU ethical principles and regulations on artificial intelligence.
- The environmental and safety aspects of the 4Sir2 smoothie pilot in companies and vineyards.
- The ethical aspects of consumer behavior research, especially with children, include ensuring voluntary participation, avoiding manipulation, and transparency.
- Potential dual-use issues related to technological development, even if the risk is low, they require monitoring.
- Responsible communication and dissemination within current legal framework to avoid misinterpretation or overstatement of results.

These issues form the basis of the ethical safeguards described in this document and must be discussed regularly throughout the project.

2. Ethical Guidelines in Research

Research conducted within the 4Sir2 project encompasses technological areas (drying, energy consumption, optoelectronics and combustion processes), the extraction of bioactive compounds from grape pomace, research on nutrition and food production technology, e.g. the 4Sir2 smoothie production, agronomic research (vine cultivation using fertilizer produced from grape pomace), in vitro gastrointestinal simulations with an artificial intestine model, interventional nutritional studies as well as market research and economic benchmarking analyses – all in compliance with law requirements.

The interdisciplinary nature of the project requires a coherent ethical framework that ensures integrity, safety, and accountability at every stage of the research process, in accordance with European standards of scientific integrity and the responsible use of digital technologies, including artificial intelligence.

2.1. Integrity and Research Honesty

All partners must adhere to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA, 2023/2024)¹, which emphasizes the principles of:

- **integrity** in research conduct,
- **honesty** in communication,
- **respect** for research participants and project partners, materials, and the research environment,
- **accountability** for the methods used and the interpretation of results.

This includes avoiding:

- fabrication, falsification, or selective reporting of results,
- manipulation of experimental parameters, e.g., in drying, combustion, or extraction systems, or in genetic studies etc.
- overreliance on AI-generated outputs, that may introduce non-verified information.

In the context of 4Sir2, integrity also requires transparency in reporting research outcomes across all experimental domains.

For example:

- Results obtained from the artificial intestine (in vitro gut) model must be reported transparently, with explicit explanation of methodological limitations inherent to in vitro simulations, including the fact that such results cannot be interpreted as clinical outcomes.
- Chemical and biochemical analyses of grape pomace extracts must include complete reporting of experimental conditions, replicates and uncertainties, ensuring that no data are omitted due to unexpected or unfavourable outcomes.
- Technological processes, such as drying or combustion or fertilizer use, must be documented with full operational parameters like temperature, time, humidity, energy input etc., ensuring reproducibility and preventing any optimisation “after the fact.”

¹ *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, 2023*

- Agronomic studies in vineyards must reflect the real environmental and seasonal variability, avoiding selective reporting of “optimal” plots or conditions.
- Legal analysis must be based on indicated legal acts or sufficiently described documents of “soft law” (guidelines, Q&A, manuals etc.)
- The potential use of AI-based predictions, e.g. models forecasting product stability, sensory profiles or nutrient release, must be supported by validated datasets and human oversight, with clear indication of assumptions, limits and algorithmic uncertainties.

These expectations ensure that all scientific outputs within 4Sir2 are accurate, verifiable and trustworthy.

2.2. Responsible Experimental Design

Responsible experimental design is a core requirement of Horizon Europe and a central element of ethical research practice. All research activities must be planned and executed in ways that ensure scientific robustness, mitigate risks and prevent harm to individuals, the environment and society.

Experiments must be designed transparently, documented thoroughly and conducted using validated, reproducible methods. Responsible design also involves anticipating potential risks, integrating mitigation measures from the outset according to the Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence², and applying the principles of the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), Science and Technology³ throughout the entire research cycle.

All research activities must therefore be conducted in accordance with:

- the Ethics by Design principle,
- the “do no harm” principle, towards project partners, participants of research, the environment and communities,
- the EU framework for Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).

Within the 4Sir2 project, responsible experimental design is particularly relevant to the following research activities:

- Experiments using high temperatures or solar radiation, e.g., drying technologies, combustion or optoelectronics-related processes, where safety measures, controlled conditions and environmental impact reduction are essential.
- Extraction of bioactive compounds from grape pomace, where solvent use, waste generation and energy consumption must be mitigated through optimal protocols.
- In vitro digestive system models, which require careful calibration, transparent reporting of parameters and clear articulation of methodological limitations, especially regarding the non-clinical nature of in vitro outcomes.
- Production and testing of the innovative 4Sir2 functional smoothie, including studies on anti-obesity gene-expression effects, where protocols must follow strict safety, traceability and scientific integrity standards.

² Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence, European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Version 1.0, 25.11.2021

³ Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), Science and Technology, Special Eurobarometer 401, Nov. 2013

- Agronomic trials in vineyards, which must protect soil health, biodiversity, and natural resources, while respecting local ecosystems and landowner permissions.
- Digital and AI-based tools used for forecasting, modelling or optimisation of processes or product properties, which must be based on validated datasets, include human oversight and avoid introducing algorithmic biases.

Across all these domains, each experiment must:

- mitigate risks to researchers, participants and the environment,
- reduce unnecessary use of materials, chemicals, datasets and energy,
- include clear documentation enabling reproducibility,
- incorporate ethical reflection at the planning stage, not only during execution.

These principles ensure that the research conducted in 4Sir2 is safe, scientifically sound, resource-efficient and aligned with the ethical expectations of Horizon Europe.

2.3. Data Management and Protection – Reference to DMP

All ethical principles related to data handling must be applied in conjunction with the 4Sir2 project's Data Management Plan (DMP). The 4Sir2 DMP contains the full operational procedures for data collection, storage, anonymisation, FAIR compliance, access control and secure transfer.

This Ethical Guideline provides the ethical framework, while the DMP serves as the binding technical reference for all data-handling activities in 4Sir2.

2.4. Informed Consent in Non-medical Research

Informed consent is a fundamental ethical requirement in all research activities involving human participants, even when the studies are non-medical in nature. Within 4Sir2, this applies to sensory evaluations, consumer tests, surveys, interviews, and any interaction where participants provide data, preferences, perceptions or behavioral information.

Consent must be freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous, and must be documented in writing or via a validated digital procedure.

To meet Horizon Europe standards, informed consent must include:

- a clear explanation of the purpose of the research and the type of data collected,
- the voluntary nature of participation in research, with no coercion or undue influence,
- the right to refuse participation or withdraw at any point without justification,
- information on data use, storage duration, and potential sharing with project partners,
- an explanation of any risks, burdens or inconveniences,

- contact details for the responsible researcher and for the Strategic 4Sir2 Project Officer, responsible for data protection.

In studies involving sensory tests or consumer evaluations, the consent form must explicitly state that no health or medical claims are being tested and that the activity is non-medical. If vineyard owners, farmers or SMEs participate by providing samples or operational data, their consent must cover use of commercial information and confidentiality obligations.

2.4.1. Alignment with the Data Management Plan (DMP)

All informed consent procedures must be fully aligned with the project's Data Management Plan (DMP), which defines the operational rules for handling personal data and consent records. This includes:

- procedures for secure storage and retention of signed consent forms,
- pseudonymisation or anonymisation workflows,
- access control and authorization rules for partners handling participant data,
- documentation standards and metadata requirements,
- procedures for lawful data sharing within the consortium.

This Ethical Guideline provides an overarching ethical framework, while the 4Sir2 DMP serves as the binding technical reference for all data-handling procedures. Any updates to the DMP must be reflected in the consent templates and participant information sheets.

2.4.2. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Compliance (EU 2016/679)

All consent-based activities must comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU 2016/679)⁴. Specifically:

- **Lawfulness:** personal data may only be processed based on explicit, documented consent for a clearly defined purpose.
- **Purpose limitation:** data must not be used for purposes beyond those stated in the consent form.
- **Data limitation:** only data strictly necessary for the study may be collected.
- **Storage limitation:** personal data and consent records must be retained only for the period specified in the DMP.
- **Integrity and confidentiality:** data must be stored securely, with encryption and access restrictions.

⁴ The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU 2016/679), Official Journal of the European Union, 27 April 2016

- **Transparency:** participants must be informed how their data will be processed, shared or archived.
- **Right to withdraw:** participants must be able to withdraw consent at any time, leading to deletion or anonymisation of their data unless retention is required by law.

Example: Sensory Evaluation within the 4Sir2 Project

As part of the 4Sir2 project, partners may conduct sensory evaluations of 4Sir2 smoothie prototypes, grape-pomace-derived ingredients, or functional beverage formulations developed during the project. Participants of sensory research are asked to assess selected attributes such as taste, aroma, texture, appearance or overall acceptability. These activities do not involve any medical intervention, physiological testing or health-related measurements.

Before taking part, participants receive an information sheet and provide informed consent. The information sheet must clearly explain:

- the purpose of the sensory study: evaluation of smoothie prototypes developed within 4Sir2,
- the non-medical nature of the activity,
- the expected duration and procedures,
- any minor risks, e.g., food allergies or intolerances,
- how the data will be recorded, anonymized and stored,
- that participation is voluntary and can be withdrawn at any time,
- that data will be processed in accordance with the DMP and GDPR.

For online surveys or digital tools used in 4Sir2, GDPR compliance must also include safeguards against unauthorized access, protection of IP addresses if collected, and secure transmission protocols. The collected data, e.g. ratings, comments, declared allergies or demographic categories are pseudonymised, securely stored and accessed only by authorized researchers, as outlined in the DMP. This ensures full compliance with ethical standards for non-medical research in Horizon Europe.

2.5. Open Science and Responsible Sharing of Results

Open science is a fundamental principle of the 4Sir2 project and a prerequisite for ensuring accessibility, transparency, and reproducibility of its scientific, technological, and societal contributions. All research activities within the project must therefore comply with the European Commission's Open Science Policy and the obligations set out in the 4Sir2 Grant Agreement and 4Sir2 Data Management Plan (DMP), including open access to publications, responsible data sharing, and the application of the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) principles.

Commitment to Open Access. Open Access Commitment 4Sir2 ensures that all peer-reviewed scientific publications resulting from the project will be made openly available through trusted repositories, with a minimal embargo period. Preprints may additionally be used to accelerate the dissemination of knowledge, provided this does not conflict with intellectual property rights or confidentiality obligations. Each publication must include acknowledgments, project identifiers, and links to deposited datasets, where appropriate.

Responsible Sharing of Research Data. All research data generated by the 4Sir2 project are managed in accordance with the project's Data Management Plan (DMP), which outlines detailed procedures, responsibilities, data categories, metadata standards, access levels, and

long-term storage methods. These Guidelines do not duplicate the DMP but fully rely on it as the authoritative reference document for data management.

Responsible sharing means:

- sharing data only when ethically, legally, and contractually permitted,
- removing or anonymizing any personal or confidential/ sensitive data,
- ensuring that shared data does not compromise the safety of participants, the intellectual property of partners, the potential commercial use and/or patentability of 4Sir2 smoothie and related technologies.

All openly shared datasets will adhere to FAIR principles and will be deposited in recognized repositories.

Intellectual Property and Commercial Interest Protection. The 4Sir2 project balances open science with the need to protect intellectual property and enable its future use. Decisions regarding the dissemination of sensitive results, e.g. formulations, process parameters, sensor data, nutrigenomic correlations, gut digital twin algorithms will be made in accordance with the intellectual property rights and co-patenting policies approved by the Steering Committee. Where results have potential industrial value, the corresponding deliverable D4.3 has been classified as sensitive and made available only to the European Commission and authorized project partners. In such a case, safeguarded access mechanisms, such as delayed publication, partial disclosure, or controlled-access repositories will be applied in accordance with the DMP and the Consortium Agreement.

Transparency, Traceability, and Reproducibility. To enhance trust in research results, 4Sir2 employs best practices for transparent reporting: documenting methodology, protocols, and analytical processes, maintaining version control of algorithms and code, providing sufficient detail to enable reproducibility without disclosing confidential expertise. Laboratory notebooks, digital workflows, and quality assurance procedures are maintained in accordance with internal protocols and are reflected in the DMP.

Ethical and Social Responsibility in Dissemination. All dissemination activities, including scientific communication, outreach activities, stakeholder workshops, or presentations of preliminary results must ensure that the information is:

- reliable and evidence-based,
- respectful to participants and consumers,
- contextualized to avoid misinterpretation,
- consistent with the "do no harm" principle, especially when communicating health-related findings (e.g. sensory test results, consumer behavior studies, nutrigenomic analyses).

The Ethical Committee oversees compliance in cases where dissemination may raise ethical or social concerns.

Compliance with the Data Management Plan (DMP). The DMP remains the primary operational document governing: data categories and flows, ethical safeguards and GDPR,

procedures for storage, access, retention, and deletion, responsibilities of each WP and partner, conditions for open or restricted access.

These Guidelines refer to the DMP for all practical instructions, updates, and implementation details. The DMP is a living document and will be updated as the project evolves, ensuring ongoing compliance with ethical and legal requirements.

Example: Responsible Open Science Practice in 4Sir2: Sensory and Physico-Chemical Evaluation of the 4Sir2 smoothie

A clear example of how 4Sir2 applies Open Science principles while protecting industrial interests is the dissemination strategy for results related to the 4Sir2 smoothie prototype.

Publicly Shared Results (Open Access): In line with the DMP and EC Open Science obligations, the following research outcomes will be openly accessible through trusted repositories and peer-reviewed publications:

- aggregated sensory evaluation results, e.g., aroma, flavour, texture, colour, etc.
- physico-chemical parameters not revealing proprietary knowledge, e.g. pH, °Brix, antioxidant activity, viscosity, etc.
- statistical analysis, methodological descriptions, and metadata enabling reproducibility,
- datasets from consumer behavior studies, market perception analyses, and non-sensitive nutrigenomic correlations.

All openly shared datasets will follow FAIR principles and will be accompanied by metadata describing sampling, methodology, and analytical procedures.

Sensitive Results (Restricted Access): Only one category of results is restricted in 4Sir2: the technology and process of producing the 4Sir2 smoothie (D4.3) including:

- formulation details, like ratios of ingredients, functional additives etc.
- proprietary extraction and upcycling processes for grape pomace,
- process parameters, sensor signals and optimisation algorithms,
- any workflow revealing industrial know-how or enabling reproduction of the production technology.

These elements are classified as *sensitive* and are provided exclusively to the European Commission and authorised partners. Deliverable **D4.3** is therefore marked as *sensitive* and stored in controlled-access environments, in accordance with the DMP and the Consortium Agreement.

Application of Ethical and FAIR Principles:

- Public datasets are anonymised, aggregated and reviewed to ensure they cannot reveal sensitive aspects of the production process.
- All health-related claims, e.g. sensory perception, consumer acceptance, or physiological/ genetic responses are communicated responsibly in defined context to prevent misinterpretation.
- Publications include links to deposited datasets, acknowledgements, and project identifiers.
- Prior to dissemination, results undergo internal IPR screening and—where necessary—Ethical Committee consultation.

This example shows how 4Sir2 maximises openness of research results while protecting the proprietary of production technology, ensuring both scientific transparency and potential future commercial viability.

2.6. Monitoring, Reporting and Continuous Ethical Improvement

A robust system of ethical monitoring is essential to ensure that all research activities within the 4Sir2 project remain compliant with EU regulations, project-level commitments, and the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). Ethical oversight in 4Sir2 is conceived as a continuous, iterative process, enabling the early identification of risks, timely corrective actions, and steady improvement of practices across the consortium.

Ethical monitoring in 4Sir2 is jointly carried out by:

- **The Ethical Committee (EtC):** responsible for reviewing high-risk procedures, issuing recommendations, and ensuring compliance with ethics requirements in the Grant Agreement.
- **Work Package Leaders:** responsible for day-to-day oversight of ethical compliance within their respective activities, including adherence to participant safety, data governance, and responsible dissemination practices.
- **Task Leaders and Researchers:** responsible for implementing ethical standards in practice, reporting deviations, and proposing improvements.
- **The Coordinator:** responsible for ensuring that ethical oversight processes function effectively and that reporting obligations to the European Commission are fulfilled.

This multi-layered structure ensures that ethical monitoring is embedded into the operational workflow of the entire project.

Internal Monitoring Mechanisms. To ensure transparency and traceability, 4Sir2 relies on the following mechanisms:

- **Quarterly WP Monitoring:** WP Leaders review progress, identify ethical issues, verify adherence to the DMP and GDPR obligations, and report any concerns to the Coordinator and the Ethical Committee.
- **Ethics Checkpoints:** predefined moments in the research workflow, e.g., before initiating sensory studies, before collecting new datasets, before public dissemination, require explicit ethical review or approval.
- **Documentation and Version Control:** all protocols, participant materials, consent forms, analytical workflows and dissemination drafts are stored in dedicated Teams folders with version history.
- **Issue Logs:** any deviations, risks or concerns (e.g., unexpected data patterns, participant withdrawals, safety risks, IPR conflicts) are logged and addressed following a documented procedure.

Ethical Reporting Obligations. Ethical reporting ensures accountability and compliance throughout the project. The following reporting practices apply:

- Quarterly Ethical Progress Notes prepared by WP Leaders and compiled by the Coordinator, summarizing ethical considerations within each WP.
- Annual Ethical Summary Report prepared by the Coordinator with input from the Ethical Committee, addressing:
 - ethical risks encountered,
 - mitigation measures applied,
 - data protection compliance,
 - DMP implementation status,

- lessons learned and recommended improvements.
- Immediate Incident Reporting. Any event that may pose risk to participants, data integrity, environmental safety or consortium-level obligations must be reported within 48 hours to the Coordinator and the Ethical Committee.
- Deliverables Requiring Ethical Oversight. For sensitive deliverables, e.g., those concerning consumer data, processing technologies, formulations or nutrigenomics, ethical compliance documentation is attached to the submission to the Commission.

Ethical excellence in 4Sir2 is supported through an active learning process. The consortium commits to:

- Regular revision of procedures in response to new ethical insights, regulatory updates, or recommendations from the European Commission.
- Deepening awareness of ethical risks through internal briefings, methodological updates and targeted training sessions organised by the EtC.
- Learning loops across WPs and insights from one WP, e.g. on data anonymisation in WP5, or safety in high-temperature processing in WP2 are shared with other WPs to harmonize best practices.
- Review of dissemination materials to ensure responsible communication, particularly in areas that may affect public perception, consumer trust or health-related interpretation of results.
- Adaptive updates of the DMP and other ethics-related documents, ensuring they remain fully aligned with the evolving project workflow and legal/technical requirements.

A clear feedback mechanism ensures that any identified ethical shortcomings lead to concrete improvements:

- When ethical issues arise, the Ethical Committee issues recommendations with deadlines for corrective action.
- WP Leaders implement the changes and document the outcome in the next monitoring cycle.
- If necessary, updated protocols, revised consent forms or additional safeguards are introduced.
- The Coordinator ensures follow-up until full resolution.

This structured feedback cycle supports a culture of openness, responsibility and improvement across the consortium.

2.7. Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Research

Artificial Intelligence (AI) provides valuable opportunities for accelerating discovery, improving analytical capacity, and supporting data-driven decision-making. At the same time, its use must be governed by strict ethical, legal, and methodological safeguards. This chapter defines the principles for the responsible use of AI within the 4Sir2 project, in alignment with Ethics by Design and Ethics of Use approaches, the European Commission framework for Trustworthy

AI, and the Living Guidelines on the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research⁵. All procedures also align with the 4Sir2 Data Management Plan (DMP) and relevant provisions of the Grant Agreement.

2.7.1. Ethics by Design and Ethics of Use AI in 4Sir2

In accordance with the European Commission's guidance:

Ethics by Design requires that ethical considerations are embedded from the earliest stages of AI development, starting with data collection and continuing through model construction, validation, deployment, and long-term maintenance.

In 4Sir2 ethics by design with use AI means:

- integrating data protection, fairness, and transparency into the design of all AI workflows;
- ensuring that models used e.g. for sensory analytics, process optimization, or nutrigenomic correlations are robust, traceable, and well-documented;
- designing AI systems so that they cannot inadvertently produce discriminatory or misleading outputs.

Ethics of Use governs how AI systems are applied during research activities. This includes:

- appropriate human oversight when interpreting AI-generated insights;
- using AI only for purposes for which informed consent has been obtained;
- ensuring researchers remain accountable for all decisions informed by models;
- avoiding use of AI tools in ways that influence, manipulate, or disadvantage research participants or consumers.

Together, these two approaches ensure that AI in 4Sir2 is not only technically robust but ethically aligned throughout its entire lifecycle.

The European Commission's Living Guidelines on the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research (2024) provide dynamic, evolving recommendations on the safe and transparent deployment of tools such as language models, generative data augmentation systems, and automated code-writing assistants.

How 4Sir2 Project follows the "Living Guidelines...":

- the origin of AI-generated content is always disclosed in publications, reports, and internal documentation;
 - generative AI is used only as a support tool and never as an autonomous decision-making mechanism;
 - sensitive or proprietary information is never uploaded to external generative AI tools without explicit approval and risk assessment;
 - AI-generated outputs are verified by human experts and cross-checked for accuracy, bias, and potential ethical concerns;
 - no generative AI is used to fabricate, manipulate, or hallucinate data, nor simulate experimental results.
- Generative AI may be used in 4Sir2 for supporting literature reviews, drafting communication materials, aiding code development, or summarizing non-sensitive datasets, always under strict human oversight and with full traceability.

⁵ Living Guidelines on the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research, ERA Forum Stakeholders' document, April 2025.

Principles of Trustworthy and Responsible AI. All AI systems used in 4Sir2 must comply with the EU framework for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence, which is grounded in three core requirements:

1. **Lawfulness:** full adherence to GDPR, intellectual property regulations, data governance rules, and all contractual obligations within the consortium.
2. **Ethical soundness:** ensuring fairness, respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, and transparency in how AI systems operate and how their outputs are used.
3. **Technical robustness and safety:** guaranteeing that AI models are accurate, secure, resilient, and able to withstand errors, misuse, or adversarial manipulation.

These principles guide the design, development, validation, and application of all AI models used in 4Sir2, including those supporting e.g. sensory analysis, consumer behavior studies, digital twin development, process optimization, and nutrigenomic data interpretation.

Fairness, Non-Discrimination and Mitigation. AI may unintentionally reproduce or amplify biases. To prevent this, 4Sir2 implements:

- careful dataset design with attention to representativeness and potential imbalance;
- bias screening during model training and validation;
- clear documentation of model limitations and uncertainty;
- avoidance of automated classifications that may affect participants in research or consumer perception.

Transparency and Explainability. To ensure accountability and reproducibility:

- all AI models must be documented, including datasets, preprocessing, architecture, training parameters, and validation metrics;
- explainability tools, like feature importance, saliency maps, interpretable models etc. must be used whenever AI outputs inform scientific conclusions;
- version control must be maintained for all models, code, and training data.

Where full transparency cannot be provided due to proprietary constraints, 4Sir2 partners must still ensure sufficient information for ethical oversight and scientific evaluation.

Data Protection and Privacy. All personal or potentially identifiable data used in AI workflows, particularly those related to participants in medical experiments, consumer studies, sensory panels, or biological responses, must follow GDPR and DMP requirements:

- data limitation anonymisation, and secure storage;
- explicit participant consent for AI-enabled processing;
- restrictions on profiling or inference of sensitive attributes;
- deletion of data once no longer needed for legitimate research.

Human Oversight and Accountability. AI systems may support interpretation or analysis, but authority remains with human researchers.

Mandatory Rules for the Use of AI in 4Sir2

The following rules are strictly obligatory for all researchers involved in 4Sir2:

- **No autonomous AI-driven decision-making is permitted.** AI tools may support analysis, but final decisions must always remain under human control.
- **All AI outputs must be validated by researchers** before they can be used in publications, reports, presentations, or scientific conclusions. Unverified or unreviewed AI-generated content is not allowed.
- **In any case of disagreement between AI output and expert judgement, the expert judgement prevails.** Such instances must be documented together with an explanation of why the expert interpretation was considered more reliable.

These mandatory rules ensure that AI remains a responsible, transparent, and human-centered component of the 4Sir2 research methodology.

Ethical Dissemination and Communication. AI tools used in dissemination, e.g., predictive modelling, visualisations must ensure that outputs are:

- accurate, contextualised, and free from over-interpretation;
- accompanied by disclaimers explaining uncertainty and assumptions;
- consistent with the “do no harm” principle, particularly for health or nutrition-related information.

AI in 4Sir2 can support for example:

- sensor data interpretation in grape pomace upcycling after extraction processes and processing chains,
- identifying correlations between grape pomace fractions and nutrigenomic responses,
- digital twin modelling of gut responses to bioactive compounds,
- analysis of sensory and consumer preference datasets.

Models used for process optimisation and smoothie production technology are classified as sensitive and follow the safeguarded access rules defined in the DMP and Consortium Agreement. All other AI-derived results may be published openly once validated and ethically approved.

Documentation, Monitoring, and Continuous Ethical Improvement. All AI-related activities must be recorded in accordance with the DMP, including:

- datasets and metadata;
- model versions and code;
- validation reports;
- ethical approvals, where applicable.

The Ethical Committee and relevant WP leaders will conduct periodic reviews to ensure compliance with evolving standards, including future updates of the Living Guidelines on the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research (EC, 2024), provisions of the EU AI Act and upcoming regulations in this area.

3. Ethical Guidelines in Medical Research

As part of the “4Sir2” project, nutrigenomic studies will be developed to assess the impact of the 4Sir2 cocktail on weight loss and health improvement in obese adolescents and young adults. The main objective is to assess the impact of consuming the 4Sir2 cocktail during the “intervention” on the following parameters in obese teenagers and young adults:

- weight reduction (both absolute and measured by waist/hip circumference and body composition using bioimpedance),
- improvement in blood pressure, liver function test results, insulin resistance, lipid and hormonal parameters, and overall well-being,
- changes in serum SIRT1 and SIRT3 concentrations, SIRT1 and SIRT3 gene expression, increased genome methylation, and oxidative damage to cell membrane lipids in obese children,
- gut microbiota composition and activity.

Patients and their needs should always be the focus of attention for project participants, doctors, researchers, representatives of business organizations, support groups, and associations.

3.1. Ethical Framework and Compliance

The 4Sir2 project commits to conducting all medical research in full compliance with:

- the principles set out in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union,
- the principles of research ethics,
- the Declaration of Helsinki,
- the European Commission's Code of Conduct for Research Ethics,
- the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its additional protocols,
- Commission Decision 2015/444/EC, Euratom of March 13, 2015, on the security rules for protecting EU classified information (OJ L 72, 17.3.2015, p. 53). Related to document ref. Ares (2025)5539845 – 09/07/2025.
- ALLEA Code of Conduct for Research Integrity,
- EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR),
- relevant national legislation of all participating partners,
- ICH-GCP guidelines for clinical research,
- the national laws applicable to each consortium partner,
- Horizon Europe ethics rules and the requirements arising from the Ethics Appraisal Procedure.

All project activities will respect human dignity, autonomy, privacy, physical and psychological integrity, and the right to self-determination.

3.2. Informed Consent Procedures

The project will implement a robust informed consent process tailored to the specific nature of each study and participant group.

Key principles:

- Participants will receive clear, accessible and non-technical information describing study objectives, procedures, foreseeable risks and benefits, data handling, and withdrawal rights.
- Consent will be obtained in written form, or through validated electronic consent procedures when required.
- Consent is voluntary, revocable at any stage, and free from coercion.
- For vulnerable participants (e.g. minors, individuals with reduced decision-making capacity), legally authorised representatives will provide consent, complemented by participant assent whenever appropriate.
- Any substantial changes to the protocol will trigger re-consent from participants.

3.3. Protection of Personal Data and Privacy

The 4Sir2 project will implement strict data protection measures aligned with GDPR and national data protection rules.

Core safeguards include:

- Data minimisation: collecting only data essential to the objectives of the study.
- Pseudonymisation or anonymisation of personal data whenever possible.
- Secure storage systems with controlled access, encryption, and audit trails.
- Processing of special categories of data (health, genetic or biometric data) based on explicit consent and legal research grounds.
- Data sharing following FAIR principles and the project's Data Management Plan (DMP), ensuring that no personally identifiable information is made publicly accessible.
- Clear procedures for data retention and secure disposal after the study concludes.

3.4. Risk Assessment and Safety Measures

All research procedures will undergo a systematic assessment of potential risks, including clinical, psychological, operational, and data-related risks.

Mitigation strategies include:

- continuous safety monitoring of participants,
- emergency response protocols and access to clinical care,
- adverse event reporting (AEs/SAEs),

- implementation of the highest possible safety standards for sample handling, laboratory work and medical procedures,
- regular review of risk management actions by the project's ethics lead.

The principle of proportionality will guide all interventions: anticipated benefits must significantly outweigh possible risks.

3.5. Ethics Approvals and Regulatory Requirements

All study components involving human participants, personal data, or human biological materials will require approval from competent Ethics Committees (ECs) or Institutional Review Boards (IRBs). Each partner involved in given research will obtain approvals according to its national legislation.

The consortium partners commit to:

- securing all mandatory ethics approvals before starting any related task,
- providing copies of approvals to the European Commission upon request,
- ensuring regulatory compliance for any clinical trial activities, including registration in publicly accessible trial registries.

3.6. Human Biological Samples (if applicable)

If the project involves the collection, storage or use of human biological materials:

- Participants involved in given research will be fully informed about the intended use, storage duration, and possible secondary use of samples.
- Biobanking procedures will adhere to EU and national biosafety and biosecurity standards.
- Transport and handling of materials will follow certified protocols.
- Use of previously collected samples will require confirmation that they were obtained with legally valid informed consent and in accordance with ethical standards.

3.7. Use of Artificial Intelligence and Digital Tools (if applicable)

AI-based tools developed or used in the project will follow EU ethical and regulatory frameworks for trustworthy AI.

Principles include:

- Human oversight: decisions involving clinical judgement remain human-driven.
- Transparency: clear documentation of algorithms, data sets and model limitations.
- Data protection: all training data will comply with GDPR and ethical approval conditions.
- Avoidance of bias through careful dataset selection and validation.

3.8. Transparency, Dissemination and Open Science

The 4Sir2 project supports open, responsible and secure dissemination of scientific results.

- Publications will follow Horizon Europe Open Access requirements.
- Data will be shared only in anonymised and ethically approved form, and only in line with participant consent.
- Relevant findings with potential clinical relevance will be communicated to participants in an accessible manner.
- No commercial use of personal data will occur without explicit legal and ethical grounds.

3.9. Participant Rights

Participants retain:

- the right to withdraw without any negative consequences,
- the right to access information regarding their personal data,
- the right to request correction, restriction, or deletion of data, where applicable.

3.10. Ethics Governance and Monitoring

The project will implement a dedicated ethics governance structure, including:

- an Ethics Lead or Ethics Work Package responsible for compliance monitoring,
- regular internal ethics reviews and documentation,
- training for all consortium members on ethics, GDPR, and research integrity,
- procedures for reporting and addressing ethical incidents or deviations.

All consortium partners share responsibility for maintaining high ethical standards and ensuring that project activities strictly follow applicable laws and guidelines.

4. Ethical Guidelines for Research in Technology and Production

Technological and production-oriented research in 4Sir2 involves laboratory work, process optimization, pilot-scale testing, and the handling of food-grade and biological materials. These activities require specific ethical safeguards, complementing general principles already outlined in section 2: Ethical Guidelines in Research. This chapter provides practical guidance to ensure that all technological processes in 4Sir2 are conducted safely, responsibly, and in full compliance with European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and EU legislation, including GDPR, as well as the 4Sir2 Grant Agreement and DMP. The focus lies on areas unique to technology-oriented research: safe use of equipment, ethical handling of biological materials, environmental responsibility, protection of proprietary know-how, and rigorous process documentation.

By adhering to these Guidelines, all 4Sir2 partners ensure that technological innovation proceeds in a manner that is safe, sustainable, respectful of regulatory and societal expectations, and consistent with the project's commitment to ethical excellence. These standards apply to all activities across the project's technological WPs, regardless of scale, ranging from benchtop experiments to pilot production trials.

4.1. Safety, Risk Prevention and Laboratory Protocols

Safety is a foundational ethical requirement for all activities under 4Sir2, specifically those technology- and production-oriented. Laboratory and pilot-scale work must be conducted in accordance with established European and national safety standards, institutional procedures, and good laboratory practices. All partners are responsible for ensuring that their research environments, equipment and personnel meet the necessary legal, technical and organisational requirements.

Risk Assessment and Prevention. Before initiating any laboratory or process-oriented activity, researchers must perform a documented risk assessment, identifying potential hazards related to chemical, biological, thermal, mechanical or process conditions. This includes, but is not limited to, work involving high temperatures, e.g. drying, extraction, thermal processing, pressurized systems, electrical equipment, and handling of biological or food-grade materials. Risk mitigation measures should be proportionate to the identified hazards and aligned with the law, 4Sir2 project's Risk Management & Contingency Strategy.

Mandatory Laboratory Protocols. All experimental and pilot activities should follow approved standard operating procedures (SOPs) and laboratory protocols specific to each 4Sir2 project partner. This includes the appropriate use of personal protective equipment (PPE), proper training of staff and students, adherence in emergency procedures, and clear documentation of safety checks. Any deviations from SOPs must be justified, authorized and recorded in 4Sir2 Risk Management & Contingency Plan (RMC).

Equipment Safety and Calibration. Equipment should be operated only by trained personnel and according to manufacturer instructions. Regular calibration, maintenance and inspection are required to ensure accurate results and prevent accidents. Equipment logs should be kept up to date and made available during internal monitoring processes. Where relevant, equipment-related data management practices should correspond to the DMP and 4Sir2 Risk Management & Contingency Plan (RMC).

Incident Reporting and Corrective Actions. Any accident, near miss, or unexpected event must be reported immediately according to institutional procedures depicted in 4Sir2 RMC, followed by appropriate corrective actions to prevent recurrence. WP Leaders should ensure that incidents are also reflected in WP-level ethical monitoring and, where relevant, risk updates under the 4Sir2 Risk Management & Contingency Strategy.

Safe Collaboration Across Partners. When activities involve multiple partners, such as transfer of materials, joint experiments or scaling from laboratory to pilot settings in companies or vineyards, each partner must ensure that safety responsibilities are clearly understood and documented. In such cases, protocols for safe handling, transportation, storage and disposal must be mutually agreed upon and aligned with national regulations as well as with 4Sir2 DMP and 4Sir2 RMC.

By integrating rigorous safety practices with the broader ethical and operational frameworks of the project, 4Sir2 ensures that all technological research proceeds in a controlled, responsible and ethically robust manner.

4.2. Ethical Handling of Biological and Food-Grade Materials

Research activities in 4Sir2 involve the use of biological samples, food-grade raw materials, intermediate formulations and pilot-scale prototypes. Their handling must meet the highest ethical and safety standards, ensuring compliance with EU and national regulations, the 4Sir2 Grant Agreement, institutional policies and all relevant project-level documents.

Quality, Traceability and Material Integrity. All biological and food-grade materials must be sourced, transported, stored and processed under conditions that preserve their integrity and full traceability. Every partner involved in handling these materials is responsible for maintaining accurate, up-to-date records documenting material origin, batch numbers, storage parameters, transportation details and any internal transfers. All records must follow the documentation structure defined in the 4Sir2 Data Management Plan (DMP) and ensure reproducibility and transparency across all Work Packages.

Ethical Use of Food-grade and Biological Inputs. Working with food-grade components requires strict adherence to hygiene protocols, contamination-prevention measures and facility-specific quality control procedures. Activities involving biological materials must respect biosafety classifications and access restrictions defined by national legislation and institutional rules.

Biological materials used in 4Sir2, like enzymes, cultures, plant-derived components must be handled responsibly, ensuring they are used only for the purposes defined in the Grant

Agreement. Any introduction of new biological materials or process-aiding substances requires prior verification of legal compliance, e.g., import, transport and storage regulations etc. and documentation aligned with the 4Sir2 Grant Agreement and RMC.

Cross-Partner Transfer and Transport. When food-grade or biological materials are transferred between partners, clear responsibilities must be defined in advance, covering packaging, temperature control, labelling and documentation. Transfers must comply with relevant transport regulations for food-grade or biological materials. WP Leaders must ensure that partner-to-partner exchanges follow the traceability rules described in the DMP.

Example: 4Sir2 International Transfer of Grape Pomace

As part of the 4Sir2 experimental activities, grape pomace produced by the Moldovan partner (Purcari Wineries) will be transported to research facilities in Poland, Belgium and Germany for drying, chemical analysis, extraction studies and formulation development. Prior to each shipment, partners must jointly define and document their responsibilities for packaging, labelling, temperature control, customs handling and transport conditions.

Purcari will package the pomace in food-grade, sealed containers, clearly labelled with batch number, date of production, weight, and storage requirements. A transport temperature of 4–8°C will be maintained throughout the shipment to preserve material integrity. The Moldovan exporter will provide the required customs declarations, sanitary certificates and transport documentation, in accordance with EU regulations for importing food-grade plant by-products from non-EU countries.

Receiving institutions, e.g., CBI Pro-Akademia and INS-Łukasiewicz in Poland, Celabor in Belgium, UHOH in Germany, must confirm receipt of the materials, verify container integrity, and record all data in accordance with the traceability requirements described in the *4Sir2 Data Management Plan (DMP)*. Any deviations, e.g., temperature fluctuations, damaged containers, delays in customs, must be documented and reported to the WP Leader and added to the risk register under the *4Sir2 RMC*, if relevant.

This process ensures that cross-partner transfers of food-grade materials remain ethically compliant, fully traceable and technically reliable across the entire 4Sir2 value chain.

Avoidance of Misuse and Unintended Applications. All biological and food-grade materials must be used exclusively for the intended research tasks described in the WPs. Any risk of unintended misuse (e.g. scientific, commercial or environmental), should be proactively assessed and, where necessary, added to the WP-level risk register as part of the RMC.

Waste Management and Disposal. Waste produced through the project activities must be disposed of using designated waste pathways appropriate for their classification according to 6R rules. Disposal procedures should minimize environmental impact and prevent cross-contamination. All partners must follow local regulations, internal guidelines and document disposal steps in line with their institutional protocols.

By adhering to these requirements, the 4Sir2 project ensures that all biological and food-grade materials used in the project are treated ethically, safely and transparently, reinforcing the project's commitment to scientific integrity and responsible research practice.

4.3. Responsible Use of Equipment, Energy and Resources

The technological activities carried out in 4Sir2 rely on specialised laboratory and pilot-scale equipment, controlled processing environments and the responsible use of energy, water and other operational resources. Ethical research practice requires that all partners use these

resources efficiently, safely and with full accountability, ensuring alignment with the 4Sir2 Grant Agreement, institutional rules and the project's sustainability objectives.

Efficient and Safe Use of Equipment. Equipment must be operated only by trained personnel and in strict accordance with the manufacturer's instructions and institutional safety protocols. Researchers must ensure that settings, process parameters and operating conditions are appropriate for the intended procedure and documented as required by the 4Sir2 DMP. Regular maintenance, calibration and inspection of equipment are essential to guarantee reliable results and to prevent equipment failure or safety incidents.

Energy and Resource Efficiency. Laboratory and pilot facilities should mitigate unnecessary energy consumption, for example by avoiding idle operation of high-consumption devices like dryers, reactors, incubators, optimizing process durations, and shutting down equipment when not in use. Where possible, partners are encouraged to use energy-efficient modes, apply heat-recovery strategies and schedule experiments to reduce repeated start-up phases. These practices contribute to the environmental responsibility goals of the project and reflect Horizon Europe's emphasis on sustainable research environments.

Responsible Use of Water, Solvents and Consumables. Water and food-grade solvents used in extraction, cleaning or processing must be handled responsibly to reduce waste and environmental burden. Partners should follow institutional rules on solvent recovery, recycling, and disposal, and describe any deviations or unexpected losses within their WP-level monitoring under the 4Sir2 RMC. Consumables such as filters, membranes, glassware, food-grade packaging materials and PPE should be used efficiently, avoiding unnecessary duplication or waste.

Mitigating Environmental Impact. Any process that generates waste, e.g. solid residues, wastewater, chemical by-products or thermal emissions must follow institutional and national regulations on disposal and environmental protection. Where feasible, partners should implement waste-minimization approaches, including segregation of biological and non-biological waste, reuse of compatible materials, and selection of environmentally preferable alternatives.

By applying these principles, 4Sir2 researchers ensure that the technological activities of the project are conducted in a manner that is safe, efficient and environmentally responsible, while supporting the project's broader ethical and sustainability commitments.

4.4. Ethical Design and Scaling of Technological Processes

In 4Sir2, technological design and scale-up activities must ensure that processing methods developed at laboratory level can be safely, efficiently and ethically transferred to pilot or pre-industrial settings. Ethical design in this context refers not only to scientific integrity, but also to responsible decision-making that considers safety, environmental impact, energy demand and the protection of proprietary know-how, in accordance with the 4Sir2 Grant Agreement.

Process Design with Safety and Quality in Mind. All technological workflows from drying and extraction to formulation and mixing must be designed to mitigate risks related to

temperature, pressure, mechanical operations and handling of food-grade materials. Process conditions must be selected to preserve bioactive material quality and to avoid unnecessary resource consumption.

Ethical Scale-Up from Lab to Pilot Level. Scaling activities should follow a structured, stepwise approach, ensuring that each increase in batch size or equipment capacity has been technically validated and risk-assessed. Potential hazards, waste streams, and environmental burdens must be reviewed and, where needed, updated in the 4Sir2 RMC. Partners must ensure regulatory compliance when moving from experimental to pilot or pre-industrial production conditions.

Protection of Know-How and Reproducibility. While safeguarding proprietary process knowledge according to the 4Sir2 IPR Strategy defined in the project, all partners must maintain sufficient documentation to ensure reproducibility, compatibility with the DMP, and transparent verification of results during audits or cross-partner reviews.

By following these principles, 4Sir2 ensures that technological innovation evolves responsibly, maintaining high standards of safety, efficiency and integrity throughout the research-to-production continuum.

4.5. Protection of Proprietary Process Knowledge and Ethical Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Behaviour

Technological and production-oriented research in 4Sir2 generates valuable process knowledge, including experimental procedures, extraction parameters, formulation methods, analytical techniques and pilot-scale optimization data. Protecting this knowledge is both an ethical and contractual obligation, as stated in the 4Sir2 Grant Agreement, the IPR Strategy and the Co-Patenting Strategy.

Responsible Handling of Proprietary Knowledge. All partners must treat non-public process information related to D4.3. with confidentiality and prevent any unauthorized disclosure or use. This includes laboratory notes, parameter settings, workflow diagrams, material specifications and pilot-scale test results. Access to such information should be limited to authorised partners' personnel and aligned with the confidentiality rules defined in the IPR Strategy.

Ethical Sharing and Attribution. When knowledge is exchanged between partners, it must be shared transparently and with clear indication of ownership. Contributions should be properly acknowledged in internal documents, publications and presentations. Ethical IPR behaviour requires respecting the origin of ideas, methods and results, and avoiding any misappropriation or unilateral exploitation.

Protection of Inventions and Co-Creation. If new technological methods, tools or solutions arise jointly from the work of multiple partners, they must be reported and assessed according to the procedures outlined in the 4Sir2 the IPR Strategy and the 4Sir2 Co-Patenting Strategy. Decisions regarding patentability, ownership shares and exploitation routes must be made collectively and documented formally.

Balancing Openness and Commercial Interests. While the project supports open science, partners must ensure that results with potential commercial relevance are protected appropriately before publication. Delayed publication, controlled-access repositories or selective disclosure may be used when justified, always in line with the 4Sir2 IPR Strategy and fully documented in the DMP.

Documentation, Traceability and Auditable Transparency. Each partner must maintain accurate, complete and up-to-date records of all technological and process-development activities. This includes experimental parameters, workflow versions, metadata, calibration logs, batch identifiers, deviations, corrective actions and cross-partner material transfers. Such documentation ensures not only verification of ownership claims and compliance with the 4Sir2 IPR Strategy and Co-Patenting Strategy but also supports ethical exploitation of results and traceability across the entire technology pathway.

Ethical documentation is essential for reproducibility, safety assessments and quality assurance. Technological workflows from benchtop trials to pilot-scale processes must be traceable, clearly dated, and linked to relevant entries in the DMP. These responsibilities form a core part of the internal monitoring duties of WP Leaders and contribute to transparent, responsible and auditable project implementation.

By adhering to these principles, 4Sir2 ensures that innovative process knowledge is protected, shared responsibly and used ethically, supporting both the scientific integrity and the long-term value of project outcomes.

4.6. Environmental Responsibility in Production-Oriented Research

Environmental responsibility is central to all production-oriented activities carried out in 4Sir2 project. Partners must ensure that technological processes, from initial material preparation to pilot-scale trials are designed and executed in a way that minimizes environmental footprint and aligns with EU sustainability principles and the commitments set out in the 4Sir2 Grant Agreement.

Environmentally Responsible Process Choices. When designing or scaling technological workflows, partners should favour approaches with lower environmental burden such as reduced-temperature drying, solvent-lean extraction or reuse of compatible materials. Such decisions should be clearly justified in WP-level records, demonstrating that environmental considerations were taken into account at each design stage.

Cross-Partner and Cross-Project Consistency. Because technological tasks in 4Sir2 project are distributed across multiple institutions and countries, environmental responsibility must be applied consistently throughout the research chain. When one partner performs drying, another performs extraction and another carries out formulation trials, each step must respect compatible environmental standards to ensure that the overall process remains coherent and sustainable.

WP Leaders are responsible for coordinating these expectations across partners, for example by harmonising temperature ranges, agreeing on acceptable solvent types, aligning cleaning

protocols, or sharing data on resource usage. This coordinated approach ensures that no single step in the joint workflow creates disproportionate environmental impacts that undermine the sustainability of the entire process.

Shared Responsibility for Material Stewardship. Materials transferred from one partner to another, e.g., dried grape pomace should arrive in a condition that supports environmentally conscious downstream processing. This includes appropriate packaging, controlled storage and clear documentation of how the material was handled. Downstream partners must build on these practices by continuing resource-efficient processing and maintaining environmental coherence across the full lifecycle of the material.

Example: 4Sir2 Coordinated, Low-Impact Handling of Grape Pomace

In 4Sir2, grape pomace is dried in one institution and subsequently extracted in others. To maintain environmental responsibility across this shared workflow:

- The drying partner applies energy-optimized drying cycles, e.g., $\leq 55^{\circ}\text{C}$, batch consolidation, minimal idle time.
- Dried material is packaged in reusable, food-grade containers, reducing single-use materials.
- All partners agree on e.g. ethanol–water mixtures as the preferred extraction solvent, ensuring a uniform, lower-impact method across the consortium.
- Partners processing the pomace track resource inputs, e.g., solvent volumes, energy use during extraction according to the DMP, enabling cross-partner comparison and continuous optimization.

5. Ethical Guidelines for Research on Market and Consumer Behaviour

Market and consumer behaviour research in 4Sir2 covers two complementary domains:

- **consumer-focused studies** such as sensory evaluation, acceptance testing, surveys and behavioural assessments;
- **market-oriented research** involving interviews, questionnaires or intelligence gathering among industry stakeholders, including vineyards, grape-processing companies, smoothie producers, drying system manufacturers and other value-chain actors relevant to the project.

Consumer studies involve direct interaction with individuals and the collection of perceptions preferences and behavioural patterns. Because 4Sir2 works with children and young adults living with obesity, this research requires heightened ethical safeguards, with particular attention to autonomy, dignity, informed consent and protection from psychological or social harm.

Market and stakeholder research involves the processing of business-sensitive information, insights into production processes, competitive practices and innovation strategies. This requires clear boundaries regarding confidentiality, transparency of purpose, non-manipulative data collection and the protection of commercially sensitive data. Such research intersects closely with the 4Sir2 project's IPR Strategy, rules for 4Sir2 Co-Patenting Strategy, and obligations to prevent disclosure of proprietary technological or market information.

Because consumer and market studies will be replicated across Poland, Italy, Portugal and Greece, the Ethical guidelines in this chapter ensure consistency, cultural adequacy and legal compliance across all sites. They provide practical standards for transparent interaction with individuals and organisations, fair study design, data protection, anonymisation, and responsible use of market intelligence.

All procedures described in this chapter are aligned with the 4Sir2 project's Data Management Plan (DMP), ensuring lawful, secure and purpose-limited handling of personal and business data, and with the Risk Management & Contingency Strategy, which identifies, monitors and mitigates ethical risks related to both consumer behaviour research and industry-facing market studies.

By translating the overarching ethical principles of 4Sir2 into concrete operational rules for behavioural and market research, this chapter supports researchers in upholding respect, integrity, confidentiality and scientific robustness in all interactions with consumers, businesses and other stakeholders throughout the project's four participating countries.

5.1. Ethical Framework for Consumer and Market Research

Research on market and consumer behaviour in 4Sir2 operates at the interface between individual decision-making and commercial realities. It therefore requires an ethical

framework that safeguards the rights and well-being of participants, protects the confidentiality of business-sensitive information, and ensures that insights generated across the four study countries are collected and used responsibly. This framework establishes the principles that guide all behavioural and market-oriented research activities in 4Sir2 and serves as an operational reference for all partners conducting sensory evaluation, acceptance testing, stakeholder interviews or market analyses.

Participant-Centred Approach. All consumer-facing research must respect the dignity, autonomy and vulnerabilities of participants, particularly children and young adults living with obesity as well as their families. Studies shall be designed in a manner that avoids stigma, pressure, or any form of psychological discomfort. Researchers must ensure that participation is voluntary and that the procedures are adapted to the needs, comprehension level and cultural context of each participant group.

Proportionality and Minimal Intrusion. Both consumer studies and market investigations should gather only the information necessary to fulfil the scientific objectives of the project. Research protocols must be proportionate, avoiding excessive questioning, intrusive behavioural tasks, or unnecessary disclosure requirements from business stakeholders. Data collection tools should be designed to mitigate burden and ensure respect for participants' time and attention.

Fairness and Non-Manipulative Study Design. All behavioural research must be free from elements that could intentionally or unintentionally influence choices, attitudes or sensory perceptions in ways unrelated to the research objective. This includes the avoidance of misleading phrasing, suggestive cues, or imbalanced presentation of information. In market-oriented studies, fairness requires neutrality toward the commercial interests of different stakeholder groups, e.g. vineyards, grape-processing facilities, smoothie producers, drying system manufacturers etc.

Protection of Business-Sensitive Information. Market and stakeholder research may involve access to production practices, technological priorities, supply chain relationships or competitive strategies. Such information must be handled with strict confidentiality and in full alignment with the 4Sir2 IPR Strategy, Co-Patenting Rules and obligations to protect proprietary knowledge. Researchers must clearly communicate what information will be collected, how it will be processed and how confidentiality will be safeguarded.

Transparency of Purpose. All individuals and organisations participating in market or consumer studies must be fully aware of the scope and purpose of the research in terms appropriate to the context. Transparency requires that participants understand the nature of the study, the type of data collected, and how the findings will contribute to the 4Sir2 project's objectives. No covert, misleading or incomplete explanations of research intent are permissible.

Cultural and Contextual Sensitivity. Because studies will be conducted in Poland, Italy, Portugal and Greece, all procedures must be adapted to local linguistic and cultural norms. This applies to the framing of questions, interpretation of sensory descriptors, recruitment

practices and the communication style used with business stakeholders. Cultural sensitivity enhances both ethical conduct and scientific validity.

Example: Cultural and Contextual Sensitivity in 4Sir2

When conducting sensory evaluation and consumer acceptance tests across Poland, Italy, Portugal and Greece, researchers must ensure that sensory descriptors, questions and instructions are adapted to local linguistic and cultural contexts. For example, in sensory testing of the 4Sir2 smoothie prototype, descriptors such as fresh, sweet, rich, light or fermented may carry different connotations across countries. In Italy and Portugal, “fermented” may be positively associated with traditional grape products, while in Poland or Greece it may be perceived as a sign of spoilage. Using the term without adaptation could bias responses or cause discomfort among younger participants.

When interviewing business stakeholders—such as vineyards, grape-processing facilities, smoothie producers or drying-system manufacturers—research teams must adjust communication style and terminology. For instance, discussions about production waste, efficiency or product reformulation may be seen as routine topics in some countries, but as sensitive or reputationally risky in others. A culturally informed approach ensures that questions are framed respectfully, avoids unintentionally challenging local practices, and encourages open and reliable information sharing.

This example illustrates how culturally sensitive adaptations support both ethical interaction and scientific comparability across the four research countries.

Responsible Use of Results. Findings from consumer behaviour studies and market intelligence must be analysed and disseminated responsibly, ensuring that they are not misinterpreted, misused or generalised beyond their evidence base. Any output that could affect commercial interests, public perception or vulnerable participants must undergo internal ethical and risk review. Responsible use also requires alignment with the 4Sir2 Data Management Plan, particularly regarding controlled access, anonymisation and secure storage of data.

5.2. Designing Fair, Non-Manipulative Consumer Research

Fair, transparent and non-manipulative research design is fundamental to ensuring that consumer studies conducted in 4Sir2 produce reliable insights while respecting the autonomy and dignity of participants. Because the project involves children and young adults living with obesity, all study procedures must be constructed in a way that avoids influence, suggestion or pressure, and allows participants to express their genuine perceptions and preferences.

Neutral and Clear Instructions. All written and verbal instructions must be formulated clearly, neutrally and in age-appropriate language. Researchers must avoid wording that implicitly signals preferred responses, frames certain answers as “better,” or encourages compliance. Instructions should focus on simple, factual guidance and ensure that participants understand they are free to answer honestly and at their own pace.

Surveys, interviews and acceptance tests must be designed to prevent unintentional bias. This includes:

- avoiding leading, double-barrelled or assumption-based questions,
- using balanced response options,

- avoiding emotionally charged descriptors,
- ensuring that questions do not imply judgement regarding food choices, weight or lifestyle.

Questions should allow participants to express genuine opinions without being steered toward expected outcomes.

Examples of Proper and Improper Instructions

Improper (suggestive or pressuring):

- *"Most people prefer this sample, tell us what you think."*
- *"Try to finish the whole portion."*
- *"This one is healthier, so you may like it more."*

Proper (neutral, non-pressuring):

- *"Please taste each sample and tell us your opinion."*
- *"You may taste as much or as little as you like."*
- *"You can skip any sample if you prefer."*

Improper (leading or assumption-based questions):

- *"Why is sample A better?"*
- *"Do you prefer the sweeter flavour of sample B?"*
- *"You probably found this too sour, right?"*

Proper (neutral questions):

- *"How would you rate the taste of this sample?"*
- *"Which sample do you prefer, if any?"*
- *"How would you describe the flavour?"*

Voluntariness Without Pressure. True voluntariness is central to non-manipulative research. Participation must never be encouraged through subtle pressure, praise, comparison with others or expressions of disappointment. Participants must know they may skip questions; decline tasting a sample or stop the procedure at any moment without negative consequences. Moderators should maintain a supportive, non-evaluative tone.

Respectful, Non-Stigmatising Language. All study materials and interactions must avoid terms that could reinforce stereotypes or weight stigma. Neutral and inclusive language must be used when discussing food preferences, health perceptions or behavioural patterns. The aim is to create research setting that does not judge or classify participants based on body size, diet or appearance.

Age-Appropriate and Comprehension-Aligned Tools. Rating scales, descriptors, questionnaires and behavioural tasks must match research participants' cognitive and linguistic levels. Younger participants, especially children may require simplified scales, pictograms or shorter questionnaires. Ensuring that tools are understandable supports both ethical fairness and high-quality data.

Cultural Adaptation Across the Four Countries. Since consumer studies will be conducted in Poland, Italy, Portugal and Greece, fairness also includes adjusting language, examples and sensory descriptors to local cultural contexts. Neutrality must be preserved while ensuring that materials are interpreted correctly and naturally in each linguistic and cultural setting.

5.3. Privacy, Data Protection and Ethical Treatment of Sensitive Information

Research activities in 4Sir2 involve the collection of two distinct categories of sensitive information:

- **personal data from consumer participants**
- **business-sensitive or commercially relevant information from market stakeholders.**

Both require strict ethical and procedural safeguards to ensure confidentiality, lawful processing and responsible use across all partner countries.

Protection of Personal Data in Consumer Studies. Personal data obtained during surveys, sensory tests and behavioural assessments must be handled in full alignment with the DMP and GDPR requirements. Only data strictly necessary for the research purpose may be collected, and all datasets must be pseudonymised or anonymised whenever possible. Identifiable information, e.g. names, contact details, audio/video files must remain accessible only to authorised team members and stored in secure project-designated environments.

Participants, especially children, young adults and their families must be reassured that their responses are confidential and will not be shared outside the project team. No personal data shall be used in a way that could stigmatise individuals, reveal health-related characteristics, or attribute opinions to identifiable people.

Anonymity and Confidentiality of Research Outputs. All dissemination activities, including presentations, publications and internal reports, must ensure that no research participant can be identified directly or indirectly. This includes removing or aggregating small subgroups, contextual details or narrative descriptions that could expose identity. Whenever behavioural data are visualised or compared across countries, formats that ensure anonymity must be used, e.g. aggregated means, coded categories.

Responsible Handling of Business-Sensitive Information. Market research activities may involve collecting insights from vineyards, grape-processing companies, smoothie manufacturers and producers of drying systems. These may include production data, technology choices, supply chain relations or strategic priorities. Such information must be treated as confidential, stored securely, and handled in accordance with the 4Sir2 IPR Strategy and Co-Patenting Rules.

Researchers must clearly communicate to companies which information is being collected, how it will be used, and what confidentiality protections apply. Sensitive market data may only be shared internally within the consortium on a need-to-know basis. Any external dissemination must be anonymised, aggregated or generalised to avoid revealing company-level strategies, competitive positions or process details.

Boundaries Between Scientific Use and Commercial Sensitivity. Data collected for scientific research must not be repurposed for commercial advantage, competitive benchmarking or informal comparison of companies. This applies to both consumer datasets and market

intelligence. When outputs may affect reputational or commercial interests, they must undergo internal ethical and risk assessment before release and fully respect access restrictions defined in the DMP.

5.4. Transparency of Purpose and Avoidance of Misrepresentation

Transparency is a cornerstone of ethical consumer and market research. All individuals and organisations participating in 4Sir2, whether children and young adults engaged in sensory or behavioural studies, or industry stakeholders contributing to market analyses must receive clear, honest and complete information about the nature, scope and objectives of the research. This ensures trust, supports voluntary participation and strengthens the scientific integrity of the project.

Clear Communication of Research Purpose. Researchers must provide research participants with concise, accessible explanations of why the study is being conducted, what type of information will be collected and how the results will be used within the 4Sir2 project. Explanations should be tailored to the audience: age-appropriate for younger participants, and context-specific for vineyards, grape-processing companies, smoothie manufacturers and drying-system producers. Scientific goals must be presented without exaggeration, ambiguity or implied commercial intent.

Honest Representation of Study Procedures. All study procedures like sensory testing, questionnaires, interviews, or market consultations must be described accurately. Researchers may not omit elements that could influence a participant's willingness to take part, nor may they frame any aspect of the study in a way that mitigates perceived effort, time commitments or data sensitivity. Participants must understand their role, what is expected of them and the limits of their involvement.

No Covert or Hidden Objectives. Covert data collection or use of consumer or market information for purposes not disclosed to participants is strictly prohibited. Researchers must avoid practices that could lead individuals or companies to believe the study has one purpose while using the data for another. This includes preventing any blurring of lines between scientific research, product development and commercial market analysis.

Transparency in the Use and Sharing of Results. Participants must be informed that findings from their contributions will be used for research purposes within 4Sir2 project, potentially included in anonymised publications, reports or policy recommendations. When results relate to commercial stakeholders, researchers must clarify how confidentiality will be preserved, ensuring that no company-level insights are disclosed without appropriate safeguards. Any dissemination must remain consistent with the DMP, IPR Strategy and Risk Management procedures.

Supporting Trust and Integrity Across All Countries. Because studies are replicated across Poland, Italy, Portugal and Greece, transparent and consistent communication is essential for comparability and ethical alignment. Ensuring that all participants receive the same level of

clarity and honesty strengthens the credibility of cross-country findings and supports the project's commitment to responsible behavioural and market research.

Example: Transparent Communication in 4Sir2 Consumer Studies and Market Analysis

During the consumer acceptance study of the 4Sir2 bubble smoothie prototype, researchers clearly explain to participants that the purpose of the activity is to understand taste preferences, sensory impressions and overall acceptance of an experimental grape-based product developed within the project.

Participants are informed that the product is under development, not commercially available, and that their opinions will help the project team improve its formulation. They are told that participation is voluntary, that they may skip any sample, and that there are no right or wrong answers. No health-related claims or implied benefits are communicated.

Similarly, when consulting with vineyards, grape-processing companies, smoothie producers or drying-technology manufacturers, researchers openly communicate the purpose of the interviews: to gather insights on market practices, production processes, technological needs and potential interest in 4Sir2 innovations.

Stakeholders are informed that their contributions will be used for research and analytical purposes only, presented in aggregated form, and will not reveal company-specific strategies, competitive positions or operational details.

By clearly stating the purpose of each activity and avoiding any misleading or incomplete explanations, 4Sir2 team ensures that participants and market actors understand how their input will be used.

Transparent communication builds trust, supports voluntary participation and strengthens the ethical integrity of the behavioural and market research components of the project.

6. Ethical Committee. Structure, Roles and Working Principles

6.1. General provisions

The Ethics Committee of the “4Sir2 Smoothy Project: Building a Healthy Drink Ecosystem to Prevent Childhood Obesity” (“the Committee”) is an advisory body established by the Project Consortium to oversee compliance with the principles of research ethics, law, and good research practices in all activities carried out under the project funded by the Horizon Europe program.

The Committee operates in accordance with:

- the principles set out in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights,
- the European Commission's Code of Conduct for Scientific Research,
- the provisions of the GDPR (EU 2016/679),
- Commission Decision 2015/444/EC, Euratom of 13 March 2015 on the security rules for protecting EU classified information (OJ L 72, 17.3.2015, p. 53). Related to document ref. Ares (2025)5539845 – 09/07/2025.
- the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its additional protocols.
- and the national regulations applicable to each consortium partner.

The committee is independent, and its opinions are binding on the project partners regarding the ethical aspects of the research.

6.2. Objectives and tasks of the Committee

Assessment and monitoring of the compliance of project activities with ethical and legal principles.

Assessment of the scientific research and development work envisaged in the application in terms of compliance with the principles of ethics in scientific research and the protection of the rights of research participants.

Taking a position on the legitimacy of conducting the research envisaged in the application, as well as its scientific feasibility.

Issuing ethical opinions on planned research, experiments, surveys, or communication activities involving:

- research involving children,
- processing of personal data,
- use of biological material,

- product testing

Included in the following WP:

- WP 2. Impact of drying technology development on the content of bioactive components in grape pomace.
- WP 3. Extraction, fractionation, and separation of sirtuin activators from red grape pomace.
- WP 4. Development of the 4Sir2 smoothie formula.
- WP 5. Study of the impact of the 4Sir2 smoothie on obesity in the context of nutrigenomics.
- WP 6. Promotion of inclusive business models for innovation and replication of the 4Sir2 smoothie.
- WP 7. Closing the loop: regulatory compliance and environmental solutions. Recommendation of measures to minimize risk for study participants.

Recommending measures to minimize risk to research participants.

Supervising the proper obtaining of consent from parents/guardians and children in the case of prospective studies.

Cooperating with the local bioethics committees of individual project partners.

Supporting partners in preparing ethical reports and documentation required by the European Commission.

Analyzing reports of potential ethical violations and recommending corrective actions.

The Ethical Committee verifies in particular:

- a) whether the study documentation and data collection forms are prepared in accordance with the requirements and principles of scientific integrity,
- b) whether the qualifications of the support staff are appropriate, in particular those collecting biological material or survey data,
- c) whether the selection of the study and control groups has been planned appropriately,
- d) whether proper supervision of the study is ensured,
- e) whether the information for study participants is formulated in an understandable manner and contains all the required elements,
- f) whether the requirements for the processing of personal data of study participants have been ensured.

6.3. Composition of the 4Sir2 Ethical Committee

The Committee consists of 5–7 members representing various fields and partner countries.

The Commission consists of:

- **Committee Chair** – appointed by the Project Coordinator,

- **Ethics Officer** – permanent member, responsible for contact with the EC,
- **Subject matter experts** – from the fields of medicine, food law, business, and scientific research,
- Representative of an industrial partner, e.g., KUPS, Tymbark, Purcari, Avipe,
- Representative of a partner university, e.g., Warsaw University of Life Sciences, UNITUS.

The Committee may invite external experts or observers, e.g., from local bioethics committees on an ad hoc basis.

The composition of the Committee shall be approved by the Consortium Council and announced in the form of a resolution.

6.4. Mode of Operation of the 4Sir2 Ethical Committee

According to the Consortium Agreement, the Ethical Committee is composed of SGGW, ICZMP and FL.

Ordinary meetings: The Ethical Committee shall meet at least once per year.

Extraordinary meetings: An extraordinary meeting may be convened at any time, upon written request of:

- the Steering Committee,
- the Coordinator, or
- one third (1/3) of the Members of the General Assembly.

Frequency and format: In addition to the above, the Ethical Committee shall meet at least once every six months, or more frequently if necessary, or at the request of any of its members.

Meetings may be held in person or by videoconference.

Decision-making: The Ethical Committee shall take decisions by simple majority. In the event of a tie, the Chair shall have the casting vote.

Minutes: Minutes shall be taken for each meeting and submitted to the Chair for approval. Once approved, Minutes shall be shared with the Steering Committee and the Coordinator for information.

Urgent procedure (circulation): In urgent cases, the Committee may issue opinions by written procedure (e-mail circulation).

6.5. Documentation and reporting

The Committee keeps a register of:

- ethical opinions,
- approvals from local bioethics committees,
- reported cases of violations.

The Committee prepares an Annual Ethics Report, which is submitted to the Project Coordinator and the European Commission.

Administrative support for the Committee is provided by the ICZMP.

6.6. Confidentiality and impartiality

The Committee shall perform its tasks in accordance with the principles of impartiality and objectivity. Members of the Committee shall be required to maintain the confidentiality of information obtained in the course of their work. In the event of a conflict of interest, a member of the Committee shall abstain from voting.

6.7. Final provisions

These rules shall enter into force on the date of their approval by the Consortium Council.

These rules may be updated during the project in the event of changes in the regulations or recommendations of the European Commission.

In matters not covered by the provisions of law, the 4Sir2 Ethical Committee shall be guided by accepted ethical standards.

7. Annexes

7.1. Informed Consent Form for Participation in a Medical Research Study

The 4Sir2 project will implement a robust and ethically compliant informed consent procedure to ensure that all participants clearly understand the nature, purpose and implications of their involvement in the study. The informed consent process will follow the principles set out in the Declaration of Helsinki, the ICH-GCP guidelines, the GDPR, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, and all relevant national regulations.

7.1.1. Purpose and Principles

Informed consent will be obtained voluntarily, prior to any study-related procedure, and will ensure that participants:

- understand the aims and scope of the project,
- are aware of the potential risks and benefits,
- know their rights, including the right to withdraw,
- understand how their data and biological samples (if applicable) will be used,
- provide consent without coercion, pressure or undue influence.

The process will prioritize transparency, comprehension and respect for autonomy.

7.1.2. Information Provided to Participants

Participants will receive clear, concise and non-technical information in written and verbal form. The information sheet will include, at minimum:

- Purpose of the study and its scientific background.
- Description of procedures and expected duration of participation.
- Potential risks and discomforts, as well as anticipated benefits (if any).
- Data protection measures, including what data will be collected, the legal basis for processing (explicit consent), storage arrangements, anonymisation/pseudonymisation procedures, retention periods, and measures ensuring confidentiality.
- Use of samples or biological materials (if applicable), including storage, reuse conditions and destruction.
- Voluntary nature of participation and the right to withdraw at any time without any consequences for medical care or legal status.
- Contact information for the research team, the responsible institution, and the relevant ethics committee.
- Procedures for handling incidental findings (if applicable).
- Information on data sharing in anonymised or aggregated form, in accordance with the Data Management Plan and Horizon Europe Open Science requirements.

The information will be presented in a format adapted to the participant's comprehension level, ensuring accessibility for persons with disabilities or limited literacy.

7.1.3. Consent Process

The informed consent process will consist of the following steps:

- Provision of information to the participant in a calm, private and supportive environment, allowing sufficient time for review.
- Opportunity for questions, addressed by trained study personnel.
- Assessment of understanding, ensuring the participant grasps the key aspects of participation.
- Documentation of consent through a signed consent form.
- For remote or digital participation, validated electronic consent procedures (e-consent) will be used, subject to approval by the relevant ethics committee.
- A copy of the signed consent form (or e-consent confirmation) will be provided to the participant.

7.1.4. Special Considerations for Vulnerable Participants

For minors, individuals with impaired decision-making capacity or other vulnerable groups:

- Consent will be obtained from a legally authorised representative, in compliance with national laws.
- Assent will be sought from the participant whenever possible.
- Additional safeguards will be implemented to protect the participant's welfare and autonomy.

7.1.5. Withdrawal of Consent

Participants may withdraw consent at any time, without providing a reason and without affecting their access to care.

Upon withdrawal:

- No further data will be collected.
- Previously collected data will be handled according to the participant's choice (e.g., deletion or continued use in anonymised form), unless retention is required by law (e.g., in the case of medical records subject to mandatory archiving requirements).
- Biological samples will be destroyed or anonymised unless legal obligations require otherwise.

7.1.6. Language and Accessibility

Informed consent materials will be prepared in all relevant languages of participating countries and will be written in clear, plain language. Alternative formats (audio, large print, easy-to-read) will be made available when necessary.

7.1.7. Ethical Oversight

All informed consent documents and procedures will be reviewed and approved by the competent Ethics Committee(s) prior to participant recruitment. Any substantial amendments to the protocol or consent materials will undergo renewed ethical evaluation.

7.2. Informed Consent Form for Participation in Market Research Studies (draft master version in English, to be adapted to national languages)

7.2.1. Purpose of the Study

You are invited to participate in a market research activity conducted within the 4Sir2 project. The aim is to gather insights into current practices, technological needs, supply-chain processes and market perspectives in the grape cultivation, drying technologies, food-processing and functional food production sectors.

Your input will help the consortium understand market readiness and potential adoption pathways for 4Sir2 innovations.

7.2.2. What Participation Involves

Participation may include:

- a short interview (in person or online),
- completion of a questionnaire,
- providing general, non-confidential information on market practices or technologies.

Participation is voluntary and you may withdraw at any time without providing a reason.

7.2.3. Confidentiality and Use of Data

- No commercially sensitive, proprietary or confidential business information is required.
- Any information you choose to provide will be treated as confidential, stored securely and accessible only to authorised 4Sir2 researchers.
- Findings will be reported only in aggregated or anonymised form.
- No company-specific strategies, processes or competitive details will appear in any publication or deliverable.
- Data will be handled according to the 4Sir2 Data Management Plan and relevant data protection laws.

7.2.4. Voluntary Participation

Your participation is fully voluntary. Declining or withdrawing will not affect your relationship with any project partner. You may skip any question you prefer not to answer.

7.2.5. Use of Results

Your anonymised input may be used in:

- project reports to the European Commission,
- scientific publications,
- market analyses and internal project documents,
- presentations summarising cross-country trends.

Your data will not be used for commercial purposes or shared outside the consortium in identifiable form.

7.2.6. Contacts

Local research contact:

Name: _____

Email: _____

4Sir2 Ethics Contact: ethics@proakademia.eu

7.2.7. Consent Statement

I have read and understood the information above.

I voluntarily agree to participate in this market research study within the 4Sir2 project.

Name: _____

Organisation: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

7.3. Ethical Risk Identification Checklist (draft)

7.3.1. Voluntariness and Autonomy

- Participants can decline or withdraw at any time without consequences.
- Instructions are neutral, age-appropriate and non-manipulative.
- No pressure or incentives that may unduly influence participation.

7.3.2. Informed Consent and Transparency

- Clear explanation of purpose, procedures and expected time.
- No hidden objectives or misleading descriptions.
- Parental consent + child assent obtained (if applicable).
- Consent translated accordingly (PL/IT/PT/GR).

7.3.3. Protection of Personal Data (GDPR & DMP)

- Only necessary personal data are collected.
- Data are pseudonymised or anonymised.
- Data stored securely as per DMP.
- Access limited to authorised team members.

7.3.4. Confidentiality of Market and Commercial Data

- Company information will not reveal competitive strategies.
- Data shared only in aggregated/anonymised form.
- Compliance with IPR Strategy and Co-Patenting Rules.

7.3.5. Fair and Non-Manipulative Study Design

- No leading questions or biased response options.
- Sensory samples presented neutrally and consistently.
- Questions do not imply judgement about food or lifestyle.

7.3.6. Cultural and Contextual Adequacy

- Materials adapted linguistically and culturally.
- Sensory descriptors culturally neutral.
- Recruitment adapted to local context.

7.3.7. Use of Digital Tools and AI

- AI tools follow Ethics by Design principles.
- No automated profiling or decision-making.
- AI outputs checked for bias.

7.3.8. Safety and Operational Risks

- Food samples meet hygiene and safety requirements.
- No physical or environmental risks.
- Interview locations safe and appropriate.

7.3.9. Vulnerable Groups

- No stigmatising language or procedures.
- Design avoids embarrassment or discomfort.
- Moderators trained in respectful communication.

7.3.10. Dissemination and Responsible Use of Results

- Outputs comply with DMP and Open Science rules.
- No disclosure of identifiable data.
- Sensitive results undergo internal ethics review.

7.4. Ethics Compliance Self-Assessment for WP Leaders (draft)

7.4.1. General Oversight

- I am familiar with the 4Sir2 Ethical Guidelines.
- WP team informed about ethical responsibilities.
- Ethical issues discussed during WP meetings.

7.4.2. Participants & Consent

- Informed consent templates used correctly.
- Participants receive clear explanation of purpose.
- No hidden objectives or misleading information.
- Consent/assent properly documented.

7.4.3. Data Protection

- Only necessary data collected (minimisation).
- Data anonymised/pseudonymised as required.
- Secure storage consistent with DMP.
- Access limited to authorised staff.

7.4.4. Market & Commercial Data

- Only non-sensitive company data collected.
- Business data stored securely.
- Aggregated reporting only; no company IDs.
- Compliance with 4Si2 IPR & Co-Patenting Rules.

7.4.5. Cross-country Consistency

- Materials adapted linguistically/culturally.
- Sensory descriptors equivalent across countries.
- Recruitment aligned with local norms.

7.4.6. Dissemination

- No personal/company data in deliverables.
- Sensitive results reviewed internally.

Outputs aligned with Open Science & DMP.

Final Confirmation

WP Leader Name: _____

Date: _____

7.5. Glossary of Ethical Terms

AI (Artificial Intelligence): Computational systems capable of performing tasks such as prediction, pattern recognition or content generation. In 4Sir2 all AI systems must operate under Ethics by Design, Ethics of Use and human oversight.

Anonymisation: Irreversible removal of identifiers so that no individual can be re-identified from the dataset.

Assent: A child's or minor participant's voluntary agreement to participate, given alongside parental/legal consent.

Bias: A systematic error or imbalance in data, tools or analysis that may distort results. Preventing bias is essential in both AI modelling and consumer research.

Confidentiality: Protection of personal, sensitive or commercially relevant information from unauthorized access or disclosure.

Consumer Behaviour Research: Studies examining participant reactions, sensory responses, acceptance, attitudes and behaviour toward food products, e.g. 4Sir2 bubble smoothie prototypes.

Covert Research: Research where the true purpose is not disclosed to participants. Prohibited in 4Sir2.

Data Minimisation: Collecting only the minimum data necessary for a specific, clearly defined research objective.

Data Management Plan (DMP): The binding technical document that defines all procedures for data collection, privacy protection, secure storage, anonymisation, sharing, access control and long-term retention within 4Sir2. The DMP is a living document and will be updated three times during the project to reflect evolving research needs, regulatory requirements and newly generated datasets.

“Do No Harm” Principle: Core ethical duty requiring that research avoids causing physical, psychological, social or environmental harm.

Ethical Committee (EtC): Project body overseeing ethical compliance, risk monitoring and review of sensitive procedures.

Ethics by Design: Integrating ethical reflection and safeguards at every stage of research design, including data collection, methodology and AI development.

Ethics of Use: Ensuring that technologies, tools and AI systems are applied responsibly, transparently and with human accountability.

FAIR Principles: Standards ensuring data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Key standard for data management within 4Sir2 project.

GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation): Regulation EU 2016/679 governing lawful processing, use and protection of personal data.

Informed Consent: Voluntary agreement to participate after receiving clear information about purpose, procedures, risks, confidentiality and rights.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR): Legal protections for inventions, know-how and proprietary knowledge. Managed in 4Sir2 through the IPR Strategy and Co-Patenting Rules.

Market Research: Research with companies and stakeholders to understand technologies, supply chains, and market readiness. Involves handling business-sensitive information.

Non-maleficence: Ethical obligation to avoid causing harm or risk to participants, organisations or the environment.

Open Science: Commitment to open access to publications and responsibly shared datasets while protecting confidential and commercially sensitive information.

Pseudonymisation: Replacing direct identifiers with codes so that individuals cannot be identified without a securely stored key.

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI): EU framework ensuring research and innovation are ethical, socially aligned and future-oriented.

Risk Assessment: Identification and evaluation of ethical, safety or data-related risks and their mitigation.

Sensitive Data: Data whose disclosure may cause harm, including health, genetic and behavioural information or confidential business data.

Stakeholder: Any individual or organisation with influence on or interest in the project, e.g. vineyards, grape-processing companies, technology providers, consumers.

Transparency: Clear communication of research objectives, procedures, risks and intended use of results; prohibition of hidden or misleading methods.

Vulnerable Groups: Individuals or organisations requiring special protection due to greater risk of harm, e.g., children, young adults with obesity, small enterprises.

